

The unequal burden of COVID-19 in São Paulo, Brazil

COVID-19 had a severe impact on Brazil but the burden has not been the same for everybody. Take a look at our research results -Beta version

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About this Storymap:

In this StoryMap, we focus on the risk connected to the COVID-19 pandemic in São Paulo, one of the largest cities in Latin America. São Paulo is the economic center of South America, and the richest city in Brazil. At the same time, the inequality is very high. This shows the values of the Human Development Index. Its levels vary within the metropolitan region from 0,479 in Vila César to 0,965 in Berrini, Jardim Paulistano, and Vila Madalena. These districts are located in the capital and

represent a rough equivalent to Yemen (Vila César) or to that of Norway (Vila Madalena), the highest ranked in 2021.

With our research, we aim to answer this questions:

What is the risk of COVID-19 in São Paulo?

How was the burden of COVID-19 distributed among the people in São Paulo?

To answer these questions, we implemented a two-step approach. In the first step, we calculated the risk score using open, authoritative and reliable data from social media users. In the second step, we discussed with local people with different socio-economic backgrounds (we call it focus groups) during our field work in São Paulo to dive into the local scale.

Learning about vulnerability to COVID-19

Here, vulnerability describes the susceptibility of communities, which is determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors. These factors increase can determine the impacts of hazards like COVID-19. In the following maps, we show that several factors influence how severe the effect of COVID-19 will be on communities

Social vulnerability index in Brazil (Santos et al. 2022)

As reaction to social distancing measures in 2020, people strongly reduced their movement radius and stayed at home. The animated map shows changes in the mobility of facebook users in São Paulo in the first year of the pandemic. However, social distancing measures were less effective in the periphery of São Paulo.

Learning about the risk of COVID-19

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Risk score including ratio of people staying at home, ratio of elderly people and social vulnerability in São Paulo (<https://dataforgood.facebook.com/dfg/docs/tutorial-identification-of-at-risk-populations>)

A more detailed picture of the risks regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in São Paulo is shown in this animated map. It combines (1) the ratio of people staying at home, (2) the percentage of elderly people, and (3) the social vulnerability. It shows that the risk is in particular high in the periphery of São Paulo. In the periphery, people applied less to social distancing measures and show a higher social vulnerability as we have seen in the maps above.

Listening to the people of São Paulo

In the maps above, we have seen risk scores on the district scale with a high temporal resolution (i.e., daily data aggregated to weeks). Nevertheless, we are unable to learn about the risk on the local scale. At household scales, there is

no scientific data source in Brazil, and spatial analysis like in the maps above are not an adequate method to capture local experiences. Therefore, we listen directly to the experiences of the people in our focus groups. The locations of our focus groups are shown in the map below.

We chose two exemplar areas for our focus group in the municipal area of São Paulo with strong socio-economic differences to capture the inequality. We are especially interested in knowing how those living in informal settlements have managed the impacts of the pandemic since geographic and social data in these settlements is lacking. Furthermore, we are interested in how the more privileged group went through this crisis since there is no tradition of research on its social class.

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Two focus groups in São Paulo.

Left: Middle-income group in the central area. Right: Low-income group in the eastern periphery.

The low-income focus group took place in an informal settlement called Vila Benfica, Guaianases in March 2022. Guaianases is a district located in the east of São Paulo municipal area. It has a population of about 110.000 people. The average income per capita is less than half the average income per capita of São Paulo. The Human Development Index for Guaianases is 0.681.

The upper middle-income focus group took place in the expanded center of the municipal area of São Paulo in March 2022. The expanded center includes the districts Sé, Lapa, Mooca, Pinheiros and Vila Mariana, which are located within 12 km from the city center. About 372.000 people live in these districts. The average income per capita lies between R\$ 909.48 and R\$ 3,757.39. The Human Development Index varies between 0.869 and 0.942.

The socio-economic situation is very different in both areas. The scenes below give us some insight of the different experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic in both groups.

The discussions in the low-income focus group, Guaianases, São Paulo

The discussions in the upper middle-income focus group, expanded center of São Paulo

A concise summary of the results from the focus groups is shown in the two mind maps below. In the first level, the results are organized in three dimensions of vulnerability. (1) Exposure describes factors that bring you potentially in touch with SARS-CoV2 virus, (2) resistance describes the capacity to cope with direct effects of Covid-19, and (3) resilience describes the capacity to avoid or recover from impacts. Level two and three of the mind map show more detailed results.

Summary of the discussion with the low-income group

Listening to the low-income group

Mobility: The participants reduced their mobility for fear of infection, due to loss of income and jobs, and increasing commodity prices.

Access to health services: Several participants mentioned difficulties to access health services: long traveling time, high transport prices, and the infection risk in public transportation, in waiting rooms, sometimes without being attended in the health center at all. Furthermore, many participants described severe difficulties to access Covid-19 tests.

Livelihood and living conditions: Many participants described that they lost their jobs or lost the state support they got before the pandemic. They described a severe situation, where money for basic needs like housing and food were

lacking before the pandemic and even more severely during the pandemic. In consequence, applying social distancing measures, isolation, and meeting hygiene requirements was a challenge. Little space was available, electricity and water were lacking and work had to be attended in person, while the transportation mode could hardly be chosen.

Health: Mental health was a major issue for the participants of the low-income group during the pandemic. Participants described depression, panic attacks, stress and sleeping and eating disorders, leading to, e.g. the need of medication, weight loss and gain.

Community support: Community support played a major role as strategy to reduce the severe impacts of the pandemic. The community support helped some participants to deal with isolation. Other participants saw the increasing need of food during the pandemic and started an association, where they helped even poorer people.

Summary of the discussion with the upper middle-income group.

Listening to the upper middle-income group

A completely different impression of the pandemic is transmitted during the middle-income focus group.

Mobility: Participants avoided public transportation and changed to active mobility, i.e. going by foot or by bicycle, or using apps like Uber. Most participants could work or study at home during the pandemic and profited from the availability of services in their vicinity. Some moved to other apartments with more services nearby, others accepted long distances to travel by bike. Some stayed mostly at home, using only the car for transportation and some bought rather online than leaving the house at all.

Access to health services: The participants had access to health services during the pandemic. They used online consultation options. Generally, the participants had no difficulties to do Covid-19 tests as soon as they were available and they used regular testing to be safe when meeting friends or colleagues.

Livelihoods: Generally, the participants of the upper middle-income group had no decrease of income. Some even mentioned a higher purchasing power.

Health: Participants mentioned increased stress from spending a lot of time in front of the screen because of home office, online meetings, and a lack of leisure activities outside. Furthermore, anxiety and stress due to isolation was mentioned. However, some participants worked with online therapy on these issues.

Opportunities: Most of the participants could identify one or more opportunities that opened up for them. Several participants used the pandemic to reflect on their career paths and were able to change or improve their careers accordingly. Others used the pandemic as an opportunity to reunite with their family for a longer time period than usual. Others used the time to concentrate on hobbies or improving their health.

Conclusion

The risk assessment identified high-risk areas in the São Paulo metropolitan area during the COVID-19 pandemic on district

level. But the results give us the impression of a clear geographic limit regarding the risk to which people are exposed to COVID-19. When we take a closer look at the municipal region of São Paulo listening to the local people in our focus groups, we see the uneven burden of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The discussions in the focus groups reveal severe differences in exposure, resilience and resistance (e.g., mobility, work, livelihoods and access to health services) between both groups. In the upper middle-income group, people used the crisis as opportunity to emerge in a better situation than before the pandemic, while the low-income group was confronted with job loss, economic hardship and high exposure to the virus. Nevertheless, community support helped the people in the low-income focus group to recover from the impacts.

Our research shows that different groups need context-specific support. Housing improvement, minimum income policies, and investments in better public transport could offset most of the severe impacts faced by the low-income group. In particular, internal support from the community itself should be incentivized.

The research behind is in the process of being published.

Acknowledgements: We thank our local partners in Brazil for their intellectual and physical support. This research is part of the COVIDGI Project, funded by the “Corona crisis and beyond” grant from the Volkswagen Stiftung.